

A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF THE COMMERCIAL ADVERTISEMENTS OF BEAUTY BRAND PRODUCTS

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Abstract

This research is aimed at describing the usage of language in the commercial advertisements of the beauty brand products. This is a descriptive qualitative method in which the data were collected from the advertisements of Pantene and Garnier. The collected data are the words, phrases, clauses, sentences that are used in these commercial advertisements. The data were analyzed according to Fairclough's three dimensional approach of discourse analysis; they are textual features, discursive features, and social feature. The results are presented in tables. The results of the present study showed that the language used in Pantene and Garnier commercial advertisements appear very interesting in building image to the audience and were successful in utilizing the various discourse strategies to gain people's attraction to buy the product being advertised. For the social practices, the words found in the commercial advertisements are considered have influence over individuals.

INTRODUCTION

In the recent age, people are accustomed with media. Media are the collective communication outlets or tools used to store and deliver information or data. Media use language in communicating to public; it can touch public in constructing people attitudes (Rohmah & Suhardi, 2020). Advertisement as one of mass media, it can be found everywhere in form of digital or printed ads. The advertisers can convey their intention through language and signs in ads. Advertisement is considered as 'persuasive discourse' because the language used in advertisement are heavily influenced by linguistic communicative means. The words used in advertisement reflect the

product on language, meaning on audiences and social practice. Cook also claims that ads can give information, persuade, remind, influence people and perhaps change their opinions, emotions and attitudes (Khasanah, 2021; Saeed & Khan, 2022). It can be concluded that advertisements do not only give information on a product being advertised for selling products but also it can change people's perspective on society, or in other words, advertisement can persuade people to buy things which they do not need. In conclusion, advertisements can construct people's identities and attitude. Advertisement is the most influential institution of socialization in modern

society. As advertisement is an interesting topic, the writer found that there are many studies concerning the discourse analysis of advertising, but there is not yet sufficient study on comparing ads in order to find out the different way used by advertisers in promoting their product. So, the findings of this research can make a contribution in the studies dealing with the discourse analysis of advertising. Owing to this fact, this study was designed to compare and analyze the discourse used in Pantene and Garnier advertisement which advertise beauty product, Pantene ads advertise shampoo product, while Garnier advertises facial cream product.

Research Objective

The present research study is an effort to find out the linguistic features, discourse strategies, and social features used in the advertisements to induce the consumers.

Research Question

1. What are the linguistic features, the social features, and the discourse strategies used in advertisement of Pantene and Garnier to persuade the consumers?

Literature Review

Literature review is a written overview of major writings and other sources on a selected topic. Sources covered in the review may include scholarly journal articles, books, and websites. The purpose of literature review is to gain an understanding of the existing research and debates relevant to a particular research topic (Ahmad et al., 2021; Maitlo et al., 2024; Ahmad et al., 2025). Iqbal, Danish and Tahir, (2014) in the study utilized critical discourse analysis to explore the women in beauty products of fair and lovely. In (2019) Hambur in his doctoral dissertation explored the Construction of Beauty Image in Beauty Product Advertisement Slogans by using Critical Discourse Analysis approach. In the same year in (2019) Kalsoom and Ali in Pakistani context study analyzed of language used in advertisements of fairness products by using Critical Discourse Analysis approach. Rohmah, and Suhardi, (2020) analyzed TV advertisements for beauty products through Critical Discourse Analysis method. In the same year in (2020) Hidayat et al. studied that how the beauty

advertisement products in forming the reality of society. This study utilized critical discourse analysis method. Khasanah, (2021) analyzed of the beauty advertisement by Make Over through critical discourse analysis.. Saeed and Khan, (2022) analyzed of language and visuals in beauty advertisements Critical discourse analysis approach. Raheem, Memon and Bakhsh, (2024). Analyzed of beauty product advertisements portraying racial discrimination; the researchers also employed Critical Discourse Analysis method in his study. Recently Anwar, and Liaqat, (2025) explored the construction of ideologies and identities in beauty advertisements through linguistic study by using Critical Discourse Analysis method.

Instead of all these studies there is still a gap left as there is no single research that is conducted to analyze the commercial advertisements of beauty brand products through Critical Discourse Analysis approach by analyzing the linguistic features, the social features, and the discourse strategies used in advertisements. The present research is an effort to fill this gap by using following material and methods.

Research Methodology

The research methodology is the process which is used by the researcher to gather data for resolving problems of investigation and design of the research comprises of the whole procedure which is conducted research (Ahmad et al., 2022; Younas et al., 2023; Saleem et al., 2024; Maitlo et al., 2025; Yousaf, 2025). The present study utilizes descriptive-qualitative method because the data of this research is in the form of spoken text. Through purposive sampling, shampoo and skin whitening product advertisements were chosen to be analyzed using the framework of CDA. These commercial advertisements were taken from social media, and were analyzed the data based on the three levels of critical discourse analysis; textual features, discursive features, and social features. The data are the words, phrases, clauses, sentences found in advertisements. In this present study, the researchers presented the data through interpretation and the description; moreover they also took some words of quotation rather than numeric as the data.

Findings and Discussions

This part presents the findings of the research and the discussion on the main points in the findings. The

textual analysis, discursive strategy analysis, and social feature analysis are described.

Table 01 Textual analysis

Text	Example	Ads
Pronoun	I strengthen my hair, like I strengthen my body. When my hair is strong giving my hair. Her skin is so radiant and flawless my skin dull give your skin up to 60 % now you can	Pantene Garnier
Adjective	<u>Positive adjectives</u> My hair is strong ... Silky smooth shampoo giving my hair the strength to be smooth because strong is always beautiful Her skin is so radiant and flawless pinkish radiance flawless skin, <u>Negative adjectives</u> .its pro-vitamin formula fights frizz My skin is dull with visible pores.	Pantene Garnier Pantene Garnier
Syntax	The all new Pantene silky smooth shampoo. New Pantene silky smooth care. New Garnier Sakura white serum cream,	Pantene
Conjunction	I strengthen my hair like I strengthen my body because only when my hair is strong, because strong is always beautiful. Her skin is so radiant and flawless even up close (taking picture close up) and give your skin up to 60 % more pinkish,	Pantene Garnier
Repetition	I strengthen my hair like I strengthen my body because only when my hair is strong , can it stay smooth ? The all new Pantene silky smooth shampoo its pro-vitamin formula fights frizz giving my hair the strength to be smooth because strong is always beautiful New Pantene silky smooth care. Her skin is so radiant and flawless even up close (taking picture close up) my skin dull with visible pores . New Garnier sakura white serum cream, (it) contains for tightening serum with sakura essence to tighten pores instantly and give your skin up to 60 % more pinkish radiance now you can have pinkish radiance flawless skin ,	Pantene Garnier
Mood Choice	I strengthen my hair like I strengthen my body (declarative form) Can it stay smooth? (grammatical question) New Garnier sakura white serum cream contains tightening serum S Garnier V Give your skin up to 60 % more pinkish radiance (declarative form) Come closer (imperative form)	Pantene Garnier
Modality	Can it stay smooth? Now you can have pinkish radiance flawless skin,	Pantene Garnier

- **Use of Pronoun:** In this finding, it was found that the first ads (Pantene) contains personal pronoun and possessive pronoun, as the producers use first personal person and possessive pronoun such as “I” and “my” to convince and persuade people to use it as a recommendation from the public figure

‘Selena Gomez as the ambassador/model in the ads’. Advertiser provides proper information about the product, using the point of view of Selena’s experience in using the product.

- **Use of Adjectives:** Pantene and Garnier ads contain positive and negative adjective. The

positive adjectives are related to the qualities of the product, e.g: strong, smooth, beautiful, radiant, flawless, and punkish. Those positive adjective refer to the value that can be experienced by the consumers if they use that product or what people will get if they buy the product. When advertisers use adjective word in illustrating the product, those positive adjective will be inserted in the mind of people/audience. While, for the negative adjective, are linked to the problems existed before having/using the product being advertised. The negative adjective found in the ads are: “frizz” and “dull”. The word “frizz” refers to hair, and the word “dull” refers to the skin. Undoubtedly, no one wants the negative conditions (negative adjective) in their hair (frizz hair) and their skin (dull skin). In conclusion, through adjectives advertisers try to give answers to what people expectations on the product. So it’s found that the advertisers use a lot of positive adjective rather than negative adjectives.

- **Use of Conjunction:** From the table above, it’s found that there are three kinds of conjunction found. They are additive, causal and adversative type of conjunction found. First, the additive type ‘and’ is used for completing and enriching information in ads when advertiser presents the information of the product. Then the causal conjunction (because) is used to present the fact about anyone who have already used and the reasons why they should use. And the last, adversative conjunction (even) promise to the audience the benefit of using the product.

- **Use of Repetition:** Repetition is also used in some advertisements in this study. The examples of the repetition found in the advertisement are presented in the table above. The underlined words show the repetition words that show repeat twice until three times. The use of repetition is to emphasize the benefit of the product being advertised.
- **Use of Mood Choice:** In advertisement, there are two participants; they are advertisers and consumers (audience). The position of participants is characterized by moods. So the role of mood is to determine the position of the participant. It shows the power relationships among participants.
- **Use of Modality:** The above show that both of ads used the modal of ‘can’ to show ability. As the use of modal to show the speaker attitude, the modal ‘can’ in ads is to show that those products have ability to bring positive impact after using the product.
- **Use of Parallelism:** Parallelism is repeated use of similar grammatical structures. It can be seen in the use of coma (,) and the additive conjunction which is found in the ads. The purpose of the use of parallelism in the advertisement is for simplicity, effectiveness, and attractiveness. So it makes the audience capture the ads’ intention easily.

Discourse Strategies

Analysis of strategy used in advertisement related to statement of the problem number 2 focuses on how the text is produced, how it is consumed, and how the power relations are enacted.

Table 02 Discourse Analysis

Strategy used in advertisement	Example in the text	Advertisement
Positive representation	- I strengthen my hair like I strengthen my body - its pro-vitamin formula fights frizz- giving my hair the strength to be smooth because strong is always beautiful. Her skin is so radiant and flawless now you can have pinkish radiance flawless skin.	Pantene Garnier
Scientific evidence/ clinical test proof	New Pantene silky smooth shampoo its pro-vitamin formula fights frizz.	Pantene

	New Garnier sakura white serum cream (it) contains for tightening serum give your skin up to 60 % more pinkish radiance.	Garnier
Irrealist representation	With sakura essence to tighten pores instantly give your skin up to 60 % more pinkish radiance.	Garnier
Emotive words	Strength to be smooth, strong is always beautiful. Visible pores, pinkish radiance flawless skin.	Pantene Garnier

These results, demonstrated that the commercial advertisers apply a number of discourse styles in endorsing their products. The strategies such as irrealiss representation, scientific evidences, and emotive words are used to influence the people. The advertisers manipulate women by giving facts about their beauty products through words which provide ‘positive representation’, the positivity of the product is encouraged by providing such scientific evidence words to present their professionalism of product and make perception because the products are proven with a scientific evidences and provide many benefits. Then, advertisers also use ‘emotive words’; this kind of language is used to connotes their power over beauty to overcome unattractiveness. The irrealiss representation strategy is used to create an unrealistic condition or a delusion toward their consumers’ mind which aims to persuade the consumers by influencing them to buy the products. In order to convince the

readers about the product, the advertisers use beautiful celebrities as models for the representative of their products as the models get their present appearance because of using the product. Besides beautiful model is presented, the advertisers also convince the readers through words which provide ‘positive representation’ and ‘scientific evidence’. Those words give a power toward the consumers’ delusion that their product can make them become beautiful. Code switching/ mixing is also used to increase a number of consumers and establish the power relationship in all communities that have a different language. The advertisers switch their language to establish a positive discourse among various communities. This is the way how the advertisers use various techniques to establish a power relationship and increase their production, consumption, and distribution in the society.

Sociolinguistic Analysis

Table 03 Sociolinguistic Analysis

Example in the text	Advertisement
The words used in Pantene advertisement, “smooth and strength hair”, “strength to be smooth”, “strong is always beautiful”	Pantene
The words used in Garnier advertisement, radiant and flawless skin, pinkish radiance flawless skin, tighten pores instantly.	Garnier

Through the words used in advertisement, the advertisers attract people to be customers. The example of the word used in Pantene advertisement: “smooth and strength hair”, “strength to be smooth”, “strong is always beautiful”. And the words used in Garnier advertisement: radiant and flawless skin, pinkish radiance flawless skin, tighten pores instantly. All these words have social significance to people in or it can be said that ads can affect public in term of social. Since Pantene and Garniers advertisement are one of the popular ads, so it can be seen in public. After seeing/hearing many times, ads will influence

public in such a way of thinking. People will agree that those products in ads will enhance their appearance. They also agree that the term of ‘beauty’ is what the ads displayed. Additionally, the advertisers present the beautiful public figure (celebrity) as the model of the product. The model’s representative can evoke the power towards people in the perception of beauty among people in society. In conclusion, the ads being studied are able to have control or power over people. After analyzing the language used in ads, the writer take conclusion that the advertisers of ads being

studied has successfully used a variety of discourse strategies in order to promote their product.

Conclusion

This study uses Critical Discourse Analysis as an approach of the study that lead to the analysis of three levels of discourse structure: textual, discursive, and social analysis. Based on the topic being analyzed, for the textual analysis, the writer concludes that the advertisers have a different way in constructing language feature, such as: the use of pronoun in advertisement of Pantene and Garnier determine advertisers' position in delivering their message in the product. Pantene builds a recommendation from the public figure 'Selena Gomez' as the ambassador/model in the ads. While the 'Garnier' builds a close relationship with the audiences as it uses second person personal pronoun which is addressed to the consumers directly and personally. Both of ads contain positive and negative adjective word in illustrating the desirable qualities and the problems existed before using the product. Those words have a strong role in influencing people in manipulating them as the adjective words construct the ideal identity of hair and skin. Both of ads use disjunctive syntax but in different purpose, it is used to attract the audience attention. There is modality (e.g. can) to show a promise of good result after using the products to the audiences. The advertisers use conjunctive and parallelism to makes it beautifully rhyme and nice effectiveness in words. It makes the audience capture the ads' intention easily. For the use of mood, it's found that the both advertisements use declarative, grammatical question and imperative is to determine the position participant. They use simple present tense in presenting the information and grammatical question to involve the audience directly. And the last, the use of imperative is to persuade people to use the products. Thus, we know that these features are presented in ads; in order to make the advertisement appears very interesting in building image and relation to the audience.

The discursive analysis, writers found that both ads use various powerful discourse strategies such as promoting through implication, irrealistis representation, scientific evidence/ clinical test proof, and motive words. The use various discourse strategies are used to attract people to buy the product being

advertised. In term of social features analysis, the advertiser used words and phrases which have social significance to people and they also can affect public in term of social. After seeing/hearing advertisement many times, it will influence public, such as the way of thinking when people agree that products in ads will enhance their appearance. The advertisers present the term of 'beauty' in their product. Additionally, the beautiful public figure (celebrity) is used as the model of the product to clarify people's perception of beauty in society. In conclusion, the ads being studied are able to have control or power over people.

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